

Behaviour of Anisoylbenzoylmethane with Phenylhydrazine

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Pond and Shoffstall¹ condensed anisoylbenzoylmethane with hydroxylamine and assigned structure (II: R = -O-) to the isoxazole so obtained; Barnes and Brandon², however, produced evidence in favour of structure (III: R = -O-). In view of the ambiguity, it was decided to investigate the behaviour of anisoylbenzoylmethane (I) in pyrazole³ formation. Compound (I) can yield two isomeric pyrazoles (II) and (III) (R = >N-Ph), according as one or the other keto group forms the hydrazone, the remaining one being involved in cyclisation. Only one pyrazole (III: R = >N-Ph) has, however, been isolated. The identity of this pyrazole has been confirmed by its synthesis from dibromide of benzylidene-4-methoxyacetophenone (IV) and phenylhydrazine.

(I)

(III)

(II)

(IV)

Anisoylbenzoylmethane (I) was prepared by Bodfors's method⁴.

Benzylidene-4-methoxyacetophenone Dibromide (IV)[†].—A solution of benzylidene-4-methoxyacetophenone (10 g.) in CCl₄ (100 ml) was treated with bromine (7 g.), dissolved in the same solvent. After removal of the solvent, the solid mass was filtered and recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 161-62 (lit.² m.p. 162°).

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1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, **22**, 658.
2. *Ibid.*, 1943, **65**, 1070.
3. Garg and Joshi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 946.
4. Bodfors, *Ber.*, 1916, **49**, 2795.

† All m.p.'s are uncorrected.

1,5-Diphenyl-3-anisylpyrazole (III: R=>N-Ph)

Method A.—A mixture of anisylbenzoylmethane (I) (2.54 g.) and phenylhydrazine (1.08 g.) in acetic acid was refluxed for 3 hrs. On dilution with water, a gummy product was obtained which was extracted with ether. The ether extract on evaporation and recrystallisation from methanol gave a pale yellow solid (yield 1 g.), m.p. 134°. (Found: C, 87.8; H, 5.9; N, 8.8. Calc. for C₂₂H₁₈N₂: C, 88.0; H, 6.0; N, 9.0%).

Method B.—To a suspension of benzylidene-4-methoxyacetophenone dibromide (1g.) in methanol (15 ml) phenylhydrazine (1 g.) was added and the mixture heated on a steam bath for about an hour. The deep yellow solution was rendered alkaline with KOH (0.7g.) in water (35 ml) when it turned red. The mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed successively with water, dilute hydrochloric acid, and water. On evaporation a semisolid mass was obtained which on recrystallisation from methanol gave a pale yellow solid, m.p. 134°. Mixed melting point with the above described material was undepressed.

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